

Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti, Perfect Guide to Qur'anic Studies (al-Itqan fi 'Ulum al-Qur'an)

Secondary source

Entered by Ian VanderMeulen, Kalamazoo College

* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Qur'anic commentary (Tafsir), Religious Group, Islamic Theology, Text, Rule Text, Scholastic text, Religious History, Shari'a, Religious Practice, Islamic Traditions

Comprehensive work by the Cairene Islamic scholar Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti (d. 911/1505) attempting to cover all areas of traditional study related to the Qur'an, including such topics as its revelation, compilation, exegesis (tafsir), recitation (tajwid), and physical handling (haml).

Date Range: 1440 CE - 1505 CE

Region: North Africa

Region tags: Europe, Eastern Europe, North America, United States of America, Middle East, Africa, Northern Africa, Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Sudan, Tunisia, Global, Syria, Southeast Asia, Iraq, England

During the past few decades, Saudi Arabia had been committed to spreading Salafism around the world. <https://www.businessinsider.com/map-of-salafism-in-middle-east-and-north-africa-2017-4>

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *Al-Itqan fi 'ulum al-Qur'an*, 4 vols. Edited by Muhammad Abu al-Fadl Ibrahim. Cairo: Maktabat al-Mashhad al-Husayni, 1967; Second edition published by in Cairo by Maktabat Dar al-Turath, 1980.
- Source 2: Al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *Al-Itqan fi 'ulum al-Qur'an*, 4 vols. al-Ṭab'ah al-iliktrūniyah al-ūlā. Riyāḍ: Markaz al-Turāth lil-Barmajjīyāt, 2013.
- Source 3: Al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *Le parfait manual des sciences coraniques al-Itqan fi 'ulum al-qur'an de Galal al-Din al-Suyuti*. 2 vols. Edited and translated into French by Michel Lagarde. Leiden: Brill, 2018.
- Source 1: Al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *Le parfait manual des sciences coraniques al-Itqan fi 'ulum al-qur'an de Galal al-Din al-Suyuti*. 2 vols. Edited and translated into French by Michel Lagarde. Leiden: Brill, 2018.
- Source 2: Nolin, Kenneth Edward. *The Itqan and its Sources: A Study of al-Itqan fi 'ulum al-Qur'an by Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti with Special Reference to al-Burhan fi 'ulum al-Qur'an by Badr al-Din al-Zarkashi*. Dissertation, Hartford Seminary, 1968.
- Source 3: Saleh, Marlis, J. "Al-Suyuti and His Works: Their Place in Islamic Scholarship from Mamluk Times to the Present." *Mamluk Studies Review*, 5 (2001): 73-89

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/1573-3912_islam_COM_1130
- Source 1 Description: Geoffroy, E., "al-Suyūṭī", in: *Encyclopaedia of Islam*, Second Edition, Edited by: P. Bearman, Th. Bianquis, C.E. Bosworth, E. van Donzel, W.P. Heinrichs. First Published online 2012.

Consulted online on 31 July 2023

– Source 2 URL: [https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?](https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA335922505&sid=googleScholar&v=2.1&it=r&linkaccess=abs&issn=10604367&p=AONE&sw=w&userGroupName=nysl)

[id=GALE%7CA335922505&sid=googleScholar&v=2.1&it=r&linkaccess=abs&issn=10604367&p=AONE&sw=w&userGroupName=nysl](https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?id=GALE%7CA335922505&sid=googleScholar&v=2.1&it=r&linkaccess=abs&issn=10604367&p=AONE&sw=w&userGroupName=nysl)

– Source 2 Description: Azam, Hina. "Book Review: The Perfect Guide to the Sciences of the Qur'an, vol. 1, by Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti. Translated by Hamid Algar, Michael Schub, Aymen Abdel Haleem." *Digest of Middle East Studies*, 22, no. 1 (Spring 2013)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: Polished parchment (most likely)

Notes: As suggested by a few recent articles in the journal *Heritage Science*, knowledge about Islamicate paper materials and production techniques is still emerging

Reference: Mahgoub, Hend, Tiphaine Bardon, Dirk Lichtblau, Tom Fearn, and Matija Strlič. "Material Properties of Islamic Paper" 4, no. 1 (November 7, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-016-0103-4>.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Notes: Many Islamicate manuscripts were prepared using rosin or some other substance to give a surface polish

Reference: Mahgoub, Hend, Tiphaine Bardon, Dirk Lichtblau, Tom Fearn, and Matija Strlič. "Material Properties of Islamic Paper" 4, no. 1 (November 7, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-016-0103-4>.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Notes: The text exists in numerous manuscript versions, a few edited editions in print, and a number of (full or partial) translations, including into English, French, and Persian

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Suyuti held a number of different posts and likely received a salary from the Mamluk sultanate but there is no clear evidence that Mamluk rulership commissioned the Itqan specifically.

Reference: Saleh, Marlis. "Al-suyuti and His Works: Their Place in Islamic Scholarship from Mamluk Times to the Present", 2001. <https://doi.org/10.6082/M1668B9Z>.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The text is not "official" in the sense of being sanctioned by law. However, al-Suyuti was attempting to critically engage and synthesize all previous, extant work on the Qura'nic sciences and thus the text has acquired highly authoritative status across many schools of Islamic thought and practice.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: Although like many Islamic scholarly texts it includes prefatory religious statements the language is overall scholastic, not devotional in nature.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Such an estimate would be extremely difficult in this case, as Suyuti's work was almost immediately taken as authoritative by religious specialists, and continues to hold sway among an ever-expanding and changing group of lay practitioners as well.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– I don't know

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– I don't know

Notes: Certain Qur'anic verses are interpreted as touching on the issue of proselytization. Although al-Suyuti is not concerned with whether proselytization is right or wrong per se, his work is including the opinions of scholars of Qur'anic exegesis (tafsir) who may be interpreting such verses one way or the other.

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Notes: In fact, secondary analyses of Suyuti's autobiography suggest that he was almost obsessed with the idea that every 100 years would bring a new "reformer" or "renewer" of Islamic thought, and that he was such a figure for his age. As such, the Itqan attempts to distill authoritative doctrine from a vast bibliography of prior sources on the subject.

Reference: Saleh, Marlis. "Al-suyuti and His Works: Their Place in Islamic Scholarship from Mamluk Times to the Present", 2001. <https://doi.org/10.6082/M1668B9Z>.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: Although not a ritual text itself, some of the topics of Qur'anic study that Suyuti surveys touch on ritual quite directly, for example rules for reciting the Qur'an (tajwid) or rules for its handling (haml).

Reference: al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *The Perfect Guide to the Sciences of the Qur'an*. Translated by 'Uthman Sayyid Ahmad and Ismail Bili. Reading, UK: Garnett Publishing, 2011.

Is there material significance to the text?

– I don't know

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Notes: There is no "original" of the text to go by, only numerous near-contemporary manuscript

copies, some of which may have minor inconsistencies with each other. Even the most widely distributed critical print edition (see reference) is not necessarily taken as authoritative.

Reference: al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *Al-itqan Fi 'ulum Al-qur'an*. Edited by Muhammad Abu al-Fadl Ibrahim. Cairo: Maktabat al-Mashhad al-Husayni, 1967.

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– I don't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– Yes

↳ Among debates about proper versions of the text, how is authority established?

– I don't know

Notes: Scholars continue to produce both critical print editions and translations of the text, or selections of it. There is no clear consensus on which versions are most authoritative. In the original Arabic there are numerous manuscript editions of the text and one published critical edition by Muhammad Abu al-Fadl Ibrahim that is the most widely circulated but not necessarily best edition. In his review of a (partial) English translation of the Itqan, for example, Andrew Rippin questions the translators' decision to rely on the Ibrahim edition (see bibliography).

Reference: Rippin, Andrew. "Perfect Guide to the Sciences of the Qur'an, by Jalal Al-din Al-suyuti, Vol. 1. Translated by Hamid Algar, Michael Schub, Aymen Abdel Haleem, and 'uthman Sayyid Ahmad.," *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 133, no. 2 (2013).

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: Although originally intended for religious specialists, some of the topics Suyuti covers include ritual practice applicable to lay practitioners as well, such as rules for reciting the Qur'an (tajwid) and the Qur'an's physical handling (haml).

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Islamic higher education

Notes: One entire volume of the 4-volume work is dedicated to techniques, rules, and principles for interpreting the Qur'an, in other a scholastic methodology toward a core religious text

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

- Ritual manual
- Bibliography
- Index

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

- No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

- No

Notes: The text does not express a legal "code" as in being sanctioned by physical, governmental (or institutional) force. However, since its original dissemination it has been taken as authoritative in its treatment of the subject matter.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

- No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

- I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

- Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?
– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?
– Yes

↳ What are the historically mainstream positions in the debate?
–Specify: Eschatological resurrection

Notes: The broadest consensus in the Islamic tradition (though not explicitly indicated in the Itqan) is that the physical body will be resurrected on a final day of judgement and sent to heaven or hell accordingly.

↳ What are the historically minority positions?
–Specify: Soul/body distinction

Notes: Some thinkers in the classical Islamic philosophical tradition made reference to distinctions between operation of the soul and body, implying the soul could "live" in non-bodily dimensions

–Specify: Reincarnation

Notes: Extremely heterodox, but there was a branch of proto-Shi'ism that existed only briefly in early Islamic history that believed in reincarnation

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– I don't know

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: God has 99 "personal" qualities as stated in the Qur'an

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: Beneficence and mercy

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

↳ In dreams

– Yes

↳ In trance possession

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: The Qur'an is regarded as the unaltered "word" of God and thus in a way the pre-eminent form of communication with the living

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– No

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Notes: Suyuti's Itqan is principally concern with how Muslims interpret (and overall deal with) the Qur'an, which is the literal, revealed "Word of God." Therefore although it is not a "gnostic" text per se, the techniques it prescribes are essential for gaining insight or knowledge of the divine message.

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– Yes

↳ What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Awareness of divine omnipresent agency and omnipotence is certainly an implied benefit of understanding (and overall dealing with) the Qur'an properly, which is the main subject of the text

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: N/A

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– I don't know

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– I don't know

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present (but not emphasized)

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– No

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– I don't know

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– Yes

Notes: Re: this question and the following: the Islamic tradition in general eschews descriptions of God and yet there are passages even in the Qur'an that vaguely suggest God's anthropomorphic existence. The eventual consensus was that these contradictions simply had to be accepted without explanation. Moreover, God is often thought of as intervening in human life in a way akin to anthropomorphic beings in other religious traditions. Therefore I have answered "yes" even though I am cautious about referring to God as an "anthropomorphic being."

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– I don't know

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only specialized religious class

– All individuals within society (Excepting slaves, aliens)

– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males)

– No

↳ Monogamy (females)

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males)

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females)

– Yes

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– Yes

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Hours: 4

Notes: The most essential ritual incumbent on Muslims is praying five times daily. Because the time of these prayers is based on movement of the moon, times in between prayers vary throughout the day (and throughout the year), from 1-8 hours

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– I don't know

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– A Faith Elect

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: I am not aware, and I don't think anyone else is aware, of any widespread destruction of the text

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– I don't know

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Not explicitly, although the text is heavy on citations of the Qur'anic studies "canon" of Suyuti's day, so it assumes a specialist readership

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: The text has remained an authoritative source unto the contemporary period, and there are many institutions of Islamic higher education that include women and where Suyuti's text might be studied. In Suyuti's day, however, Islamic education was overwhelmingly male, and the sources he refers to also reflect this.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– I don't know

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Notes: Although the text does not specify the nature of any such benefit, there is a strongly implied, general social benefit to following many of the ethical proscriptions in the text, i.e. how one studies and handles the Qur'an

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– I don't know

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti, Perfect Guide to Qur'anic Studies (al-Itqan fi 'Ulum al-Qur'an), Saleh, Marlis. "Al-suyuti and His Works: Their Place in Islamic Scholarship from Mamluk Times to the Present", 2001. <https://doi.org/10.6082/M1668B9Z>.

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Reference: Jalal al-Din al-Suyuti, Perfect Guide to Qur'anic Studies (al-Itqan fi 'Ulum al-Qur'an), al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. Le Parfait Manuel Des Sciences Coraniques Al-itqan Fi 'ulum Al-qur'an De Galal Al-din Al-suyuti. Translated by Michel Lagarde. Leiden: Brill, 2018.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Saleh, Marlis. "Al-suyuti and His Works: Their Place in Islamic Scholarship from Mamluk Times to the Present", 2001. <https://doi.org/10.6082/M1668B9Z>.

Reference: Specify: Polished parchment (most likely), Mahgoub, Hend, Tiphaine Bardon, Dirk Lichtblau, Tom Fearn, and Matija Strlič. "Material Properties of Islamic Paper" 4, no. 1 (November 7, 2016). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-016-0103-4>. ,

Reference: No, al-Suyuti, Jalal al-Din. *The Perfect Guide to the Sciences of the Qur'an*. Translated by 'Uthman Sayyid Ahmad and Ismail Bili. Reading, UK: Garnett Publishing, 2011.

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Reference: I don't know, Rippin, Andrew. "Perfect Guide to the Sciences of the Qur'an, by Jalal Al-din Al-suyuti, Vol. 1. Translated by Hamid Algar, Michael Schub, Aymen Abdel Haleem, and 'uthman Sayyid Ahmad.", *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 133, no. 2 (2013).